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Traditional Folklore in the Spanish and Uzbek Languages

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***Abstract:** This article provides a comparative analysis of the features of traditional oral folk art in the Spanish and Uzbek languages. Folklore is an important part of national culture, reflecting the historical, social, and spiritual heritage of the people. The article examines the genres, stylistic and semantic features of Spanish and Uzbek folklore, as well as their means of artistic expression. According to the research results, it is revealed that, although oral folk art in both languages has common features, it also has its own peculiarities due to the national mentality and historical conditions. The article is aimed at highlighting the significance of oral folk art from a linguistic and cultural point of view and is based on the method of comparative analysis.*

***Key words:** folklore, Spanish, Uzbek, stylistics, semantics, comparative analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Folklore is one of the important factors reflecting the cultural heritage and spiritual world of each nation. This creative process was formed over the centuries and expressed the lifestyle, customs, beliefs, and worldview of the people. Although the oral creative traditions of each nation have their own peculiarities, there are also common aspects between them. This research is aimed at a comparative analysis of the semantic and stylistic features of traditional folklore in the Spanish and Uzbek languages. The oral creativity of the Spanish and Uzbek peoples is distinguished by its historical roots, cultural aspects, and artistic means. In this article, examples of oral folk art belonging to both languages are analyzed, and their genre features, lexical-semantic and stylistic aspects are studied.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The study of folklore and its linguistic, stylistic, and semantic aspects is widely covered in scientific literature. Folklore is studied from the point of view of folklore, linguistics, and literary studies as the cultural and linguistic heritage of different peoples. Vladimir Propp (1928) studied the structure and semantic features of folk tales and proposed universal schemes. A.N. Veselovsky studied the evolution of artistic structures through a historical-comparative analysis of folk art. In Uzbek literary studies, Sh. Sirojiddinov, H. Boltayev, and M. Jo'rayev analyzed the genre characteristics of folk oral art.

Scientific sources on oral folk art in the Spanish language were mainly studied by Spanish, Latin American, and other foreign scholars. J. Casares and R. Menéndez Pidal studied the stylistic and semantic aspects of Spanish folk poetry and fairy tales. Antonio Rodríguez Almodóvar also showed the historical roots of Spanish fairy tales and their influence on modern literature. These studies are aimed at revealing the poetic and linguistic aspects of Spanish folklore. Uzbek folklore has been studied by many local and international scholars. In the analysis of the semantic and stylistic aspects of dastans, fairy tales, proverbs, and sayings in Uzbek folklore, the works of such scholars as H. Ziyaev, M. Zhuraev, and B. Sarimsakov deserve special attention. They studied the spiritual and artistic features of oral folk art, as well as its interrelationship with written literature.

Methodology

In this study, a comparative analysis of the semantic and stylistic features of Spanish and Uzbek folklore was carried out. The main methods are the comparative-historical method, the method of linguistic-stylistic analysis, and the methods of discursive analysis; the comparative-historical method was used to compare the genres of Spanish and Uzbek folklore and to analyze the stages of their development. The method of linguistic-stylistic analysis was used to study the lexical, semantic, and artistic means of expression of texts. Discursive analysis helped to determine the socio-cultural context of examples of oral folk art.

RESULTS

The results of the study showed that Spanish and Uzbek folklore have a number of similarities and differences, the formation of which is associated with historical, social, and cultural factors.

Spanish and Uzbek folklore have similarities in several aspects. For example, the diversity of genres, that is, the oral creativity of both peoples includes different genres, including fairy tales, epics, legends, proverbs, riddles, and songs. Also, the didactic character, that is, Spanish and Uzbek oral folk art, is aimed at preserving the rules of etiquette, spiritual values, and historical memory. For example, in Spanish fairy tales, honesty, courage, and wisdom are promoted, while in Uzbek fairy tales, diligence, generosity, and justice are reflected as values. In addition, there are archetypal images, that is, universal heroes in both folklores. For example, in Spanish folklore, there are images of "pícaro" (cunning boy) and knightly heroes, while in Uzbek folklore, such images as a smart orphan boy, a wise old man, or a cunning old woman are widespread.

Also, based on the research results, it was established that there are a number of main differences between Spanish and Uzbek folklore.

Differences in genre system

In Uzbek oral folk art, the tradition of epic poetry is developed. Dastans are often performed by soloists with musical accompaniment (for example, "Alpamysh"). In Spanish folklore, ballads and "romance" are widespread, often illuminating themes of heroism or love. Proverbs and wise sayings

are of great importance in Uzbek folklore. Proverbs are also common in Spanish culture, but most of them have a religious and historical context.

Means of artistic expression

Spanish folklore tends to use metaphorical and poetic language. Poetic style, rhyming lines, and allegorical images are widely used in Spanish ballads. For example, in the folk songs of the collection "Romancero," the themes of love, heroism, and tragedy are expressed poetically. In Uzbek folklore, proverbs and wise sayings prevail. For example, proverbs such as "Those who do the work of the people are beloved by the people" or "Work brings comfort" reflect important experiences of people's lives.

Differences in cultural context

Spanish folklore is largely based on religious and chivalric traditions. For example, in Spanish fairy tales, Christian ideas, the motif of sacred heroes and angels are widespread. Uzbek oral folk art is connected with the culture of nomadism and agriculture. For example, many epics and legends cover the themes of animal husbandry, courage, and freedom.

The research results show that although Spanish and Uzbek oral folk art developed differently according to cultural and linguistic features, their main goal is the same - to preserve and transmit the spiritual values of the people to future generations. These results will serve as an important theoretical basis for future comparative folklore and linguistic research.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study revealed the commonalities and differences between Spanish and Uzbek folklore. During the discussion, the reasons for these similarities and differences, as well as their linguistic, cultural, and social significance, are analyzed.

Causes of common features

There are many similarities between Spanish and Uzbek folklore, which is explained by several factors. Firstly, universal folklore laws, that is, oral folk art, serve as a means of promoting moral values in any society, implementing educational and didactic goals. Secondly, the similarity of mythological roots, that is, in many folk tales and legends, there are universal archetypes (for example, hero, evil force, magical helper), which is characteristic of both cultures. Thirdly, the social structure of society, that is, the Spanish and Uzbek peoples, historically formed in societies based on agriculture and a collective lifestyle. This led to the priority of collective values in their oral creativity.

Causes of differences

The research results show that the differences between Spanish and Uzbek folklore are related to historical, social, and cultural factors. Historical context - while Spanish folklore developed more under the influence of chivalry, religious wars, and Christianity, Uzbek folklore is associated with nomadism, agriculture, and Eastern cultural heritage. The style of artistic expression - Spanish folklore is based on poetic rules and rhyme, and poetic forms are widespread. In Uzbek folklore, proverbs, riddles, and wise sayings are more common. Religious influence - while Catholic ideas and religious symbols are often found in Spanish folk tales, Islamic values and Eastern wisdom occupy a central place in Uzbek folklore.

CONCLUSION

This study helped to determine their cultural, linguistic, and educational significance through a comparative analysis of the similarities and differences between Spanish and Uzbek folklore. The obtained results are important for folklore research, linguistics, and cultural studies, and will serve as a basis for conducting a more comprehensive comparative analysis of folklore in the future. The results show that Spanish and Uzbek folklore is not only an expression of their national culture, but also a literary heritage reflecting universal human values. Therefore, their study and comparison are of great importance for linguistic and cultural research.

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